

Concerted European action on Sustainable Applications of REfractories

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement no.101072625

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Deliverable D6.3 - Report about Scientific Publications

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**Funded by
the European Union**

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History of Changes for this Deliverable

Version	Date	Author (Organization)	Inputs / Changes
v 1.00	28/09/2023	Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	First draft
v 1.10	16/10/2024	Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Final contribution of PhDs added

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1 Introduction

As part of the CESAREF training program, the 15 Doctoral Candidates (DCs) have the opportunity to disseminate the results of their cutting-edge research through international journals and international conferences across the globe. While at the mid-point of the project the CESAREF DCs have already participated in conferences in places ranging from Panama to Croatia and have published their work in Rank A journals such as the Journal of the European Ceramic Society, IEEE Access and Steel Research International. These published results are also openly available via the CESAREF website and on the Zenodo platform. This deliverable will highlight the international conferences attended by the DCs, and give a global overview of the published scientific papers and the plans for future publication.

2 International conferences

The 15 CESAREF DCs have already participated in a selection of international conferences such as UNITECR (UNified International Technical Conference of Refractories), ECerS (European Ceramic Society) and the International Colloquium on Refractories. Before the end of 2024, CESAREF DCs will also be participating in the Wuhan Symposium on Refractories, the International Symposium on Refractories (ISR2024) in Chengdu, China and the IREFCON, Goa, India. These conferences are listed in the table below.

DC	International conference
01	Sarah, BADIOLI, Thibault CHAMPION, Léna ROUMIGUIER, Marielle DARGAUD, Angélique LEONARD Prospective LCA on the Design of New Refractories for a Greener Steelmaking Process (Poster) SETAC Europe 33rd annual meeting, 2023, Dublin, Ireland
	Sarah, BADIOLI, Thibault CHAMPION, Léna ROUMIGUIER, Marielle DARGAUD, Angélique LEONARD Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and eco design: towards optimized refractory materials for a green steelmaking process (Poster) European Ceramic Society, 2023, Lyon, France
	Sarah, BADIOLI, Thibault CHAMPION, Marielle DARGAUD, Angélique LEONARD State of the Art, Challenges and Future Development of Environmental Assessments of Magnesia Supply Chain (Poster) SETAC Europe 34rd annual meeting, 2024, Sevilla, Spain
	Sarah, BADIOLI, Thibault CHAMPION, Marielle DARGAUD, Angélique LEONARD Enhancing Data Quality for Robust Life Cycle Assessment in Refractory Industry: Strategies and Implications (Poster) International Colloquium on Refractories, 2024, Aachen, Germany
02	João V. MENEZES CUNHA, Eric PIRARD, Thomas DRNEK Revisiting Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP) to assess the risk of depletion of Magnesium (Poster) LCM 2023, Lille, France
	João V. MENEZES CUNHA, Eric PIRARD, Thomas DRNEK Overview on LCA: Challenges and Opportunities for the Refractory Industry (Presentation) Unified International Technical Conference on Refractories, 2023, Frankfurt, Germany
03	MD JUBAYED, Rinus SIEBRING, Angélique LEONARD The Choice of Refractories for Steel Ladle Lining: a Life Cycle Perspective (Poster) SETAC Europe 33rd annual meeting, 2023, Dublin, Ireland
	MD JUBAYED, Rinus SIEBRING, Angélique LEONARD The choice of magnesia-carbon refractories for steel ladle lining: a life cycle perspective (Poster) LCM 2023, Lille, France
	MD JUBAYED, Rinus SIEBRING, Angélique LEONARD The choice of magnesia-carbon refractories for steel ladle lining: a life cycle perspective (Poster) Unified International Technical Conference on Refractories, 2023, Frankfurt, Germany
04	Mathilda DERENSY, Thorsten TONNESEN, Jong-Won SHIN, Jesus GONZALEZ-JULIAN Use of metallurgical residues as potential raw materials for high performance refractory castables (Poster) European Ceramic Society, 2023, Lyon, France
	Mathilda DERENSY, Thorsten TONNESEN, Jong-Won SHIN, Jesus GONZALEZ-JULIAN Use of metallurgical residues as potential raw materials for high performance refractory castables (Poster) Unified International Technical Conference on Refractories, 2023, Frankfurt, Germany

	Mathilda DERENSY, Thorsten TONNESEN, Jong-Won SHIN, Jesus GONZALEZ-JULIAN Use of metallurgical residues as potential raw materials for high performance refractory castables (Presentation) International Colloquium on Refractories, 2024, Aachen, Germany
05	Andrea SALERNO, Martiniano PICICCO, Elsa THUNE, Nicolas TESSIER-DOYEN, Severine ROMERO-BAIVIER, Lionel REBOUILLAT, Marc HUGER EU Green Deal steelmaking challenges: recycling, reuse, hydrogen & artificial intelligence (Presentation) IMFORMED Mineral Recycling Forum 2023, Dubrovnik, Croatia
	Andrea SALERNO, Martiniano PICICCO, Elsa THUNE, Nicolas TESSIER-DOYEN, Severine ROMERO-BAIVIER, Lionel REBOUILLAT, Marc HUGER Reuse and recyclability of refractories from steel industry (Poster) European Ceramic Society, 2023, Lyon, France
	Andrea SALERNO, Martiniano PICICCO, Elsa THUNE, Nicolas TESSIER-DOYEN, Severine ROMERO-BAIVIER, Lionel REBOUILLAT, Marc HUGER Insights on numerical models to predict potential recyclability of spent refractories from steel making industry (Presentation) Unified International Technical Conference on Refractories, 2023, Frankfurt, Germany
06	Kwasi BOATENG, Jean-Michel AUVRAY, Christoph WÖHRMEYER, Elsa THUNE, Nicolas TESSIER-DOYEN, Marc HUGER Effects of Grain Size and Shape of alumina aggregates on the Sinterability and Thermal Shock Resistance of Refractory Materials (Poster) European Ceramic Society, 2023, Lyon, France
	Kwasi BOATENG, Jean-Michel AUVRAY, Christoph WÖHRMEYER, Elsa THUNE, Nicolas TESSIER-DOYEN, Marc HUGER Microstructure Design of a More Sustainable Alumina-Spinel Refractory Castable (Poster) Unified International Technical Conference on Refractories, 2023, Frankfurt, Germany
07	Molla EWNETE, Olivier CASTELNAU, Hong PENG, Elsa THUNE, Rene GUINEBRETIERE Alumina-magnesia reactive sintering kinetics and for innovative refractory ceramics at high temperatures (Poster) International Colloquium on Refractories, 2024, Aachen, Germany
08	Harikeshava RANGANATHAN, Ratana SOTH, Christoph WÖHRMEYER, Damien ANDRE, Marc HUGER Investigation of relationships between microstructure and thermomechanical properties of refractory material using the Discrete element method (DEM) (Poster) European Ceramic Society, 2023, Lyon, France
	Harikeshava RANGANATHAN, Ratana SOTH, Christoph WÖHRMEYER, Damien ANDRE, Marc HUGER Discrete Element Method (DEM) to support microstructure design of refractories (Poster) Unified International Technical Conference on Refractories, 2023, Frankfurt, Germany
	Harikeshava RANGANATHAN, Damien ANDRE, Mossaab MOUIYA, Marc HUGER, Ratana SOTH, Christoph WÖHRMEYER Discrete-element modeling of aluminum titanate microstructure (Presentation) GFC, 2024, Limoges, France
	Harikeshava RANGANATHAN, Damien ANDRE, Mossaab MOUIYA, Marc HUGER, Ratana SOTH, Christoph WÖHRMEYER Novel tool to perform thermomechanical characterisation on refractory microstructure design using Discrete Element Method (DEM) (Presentation) CIMTEC, 2024, Montecatini Terme, Italy
	Damien ANDRE, Quentin PLEDAEL, Harikeshava RANGANATHAN, Mossaab MOUIYA, Nicolas TESSIER-DOYEN, Marc HUGER, Ratana SOTH, Christoph WÖHRMEYER Modélisation par éléments discrets de l'endommagement généré par anisotropie de dilatation thermique d'une céramique réfractaire (Presentation) CSMA, 2024, Giens, France
09	Michiel SMEDES, Wen ZHANG, Dietmar GRUBER Design of a New Ceramic Castable for Investment Casting of Turbine Blades (Presentation) Pan American Ceramics Congress and Ferroelectrics Meeting of Americas - PACC-FMAs, 2024, Panama City, Panama
	Michiel SMEDES, Wen ZHANG, Dietmar GRUBER, Aliz PINTO MORA Design of a New Ceramic Castable for Investment Casting of Turbine Blades (Presentation) The 7th International Postgraduates Seminar on Refractories, 2024, Wuhan, China
10	Paula CAMPOS DE OLIVEIRA, Wen ZHANG, Henning MARKÖTTER, Clément REMACHA, Giovanni BRUNO Influence of processing on the microstructure of aerospace ceramics by imaging (Presentation) Pan American Ceramics Congress and Ferroelectrics Meeting of Americas - PACC-FMAs, 2024, Panama City, Panama
11	Cristian BOHORQUEZ, Dietmar GRUBER Microstructural changes in high alumina refractory due to hydrogen exposure (Presentation) International Colloquium on Refractories: ICR 2024, Aachen, Germany
	Cristian BOHORQUEZ, Dietmar GRUBER Hydrogen Exposure Impact on a Phosphate-Bonded High Alumina Refractory (Presentation) 7th International Postgraduates Seminar on Refractories, Wuhan, China (online)
	Cristian BOHORQUEZ, Dietmar GRUBER, Sido SINNEMA Characterization of refractories with regard to the application in H₂-containing atmospheres Unified International Technical Conference on Refractories - 2023, Frankfurt, Germany
12	Milena RIBEIRO GOMES, Antoine DUCASTEL, Lukas KONRAD, Taco JANNSEN, Erick ESTRADA OSPINO Hydrogen-resistant refractories for direct reduced iron production (Presentation) ESTAD - European Steel Technology and Application Days, 2023, Düsseldorf, Germany

	Milena RIBEIRO GOMES Hydrogène en sidérurgie: État de l'art, exigences et défis pour les matériaux réfractaires (Presentation) Journées Réfractaires - GFC, 2024, Limoges, France
	Milena RIBEIRO GOMES, Thorsten TONNESEN, Daniela GAVAGNIN Use of Hydrogen in Steelmaking: Implications for Refractory Materials (Presentation) International Colloquium on Refractories, 2024, Aachen, Germany
13	Amit Kumar GOPE, Alexandre BOULLE, Johan RICHAUD, Felix BIRKELBACH, Lionel REBOUILLAT, Severine ROMERO BAIVIER, Marc HUGER Prediction of performance and assessment of reusability and recycling of refractory materials using non-destructive online evaluation and machine learning algorithms) (Poster) European Ceramic Society, 2023, Lyon, France
	Amit Kumar GOPE, Alexandre BOULLE, Johan RICHAUD, Felix BIRKELBACH, Lionel REBOUILLAT, Severine ROMERO BAIVIER, Marc HUGER Performance prediction and assessment of reusability and recycling of refractory materials using the NDT sensing approach and Machine Learning) (Poster) Unified International Technical Conference on Refractories, 2023, Frankfurt, Germany
14	Fatemeh AZIZI, Marvin GENNESSON, Damien WAGNER, Felix BIRKELBACH, René HOFMANN Enhancing Steel Ladle Thermal Management: Implementing a Model Order Reduction Approach for Temperature Monitoring. International Colloquium on Refractories, 2024, Aachen, Germany
15	Victor RUELA, Paul van BEURDEN, Sido SINNEMA, Rene HOFMANN, Felix BIRKELBACH Advanced Analytics Applied to Improve the Energy Efficiency of Steel Ladle Logistics (Poster) Unified International Technical Conference on Refractories, 2023, Frankfurt, Germany
	Victor RUELA, Paul van BEURDEN, Rene HOFMANN, Felix BIRKELBACH A heuristic for fitting piecewise-linear models of bivariate functions with simplices and its application to an industrial use case (Presentation) 33rd European Conference on Operational Research - EURO24, 2024, Copenhagen, Denmark

3 Scientific publications - Accepted, Submitted and Planned

Each DC is aiming to publish at least 3 high quality publications as a result of the research they have undertaken. The DCs all have a clear view of the direction of their research and a plan for individual publications has been discussed with their local supervisory team. These planned publications are indicated in the table below. Typically for research projects of this nature publications would be produced towards the end of the research period, however, some CESAREF DCs have already submitted and had accepted publications, even at the mid-point of the project, these publications are also indicated in the table below.

DC	Peer reviewed papers
01	1 João Victor MENEZES CUNHA, Eric PIRARD, Thomas DRNEK; Bridging the gap between geospheric and anthropospheric mineral resources: A unified framework to support their sustainable management; Submitted - The Extractive Industries and Society.
	2 João Victor MENEZES CUNHA, Sarah BADIOLI, Eric PIRARD, Thomas DRNEK; Magnesia: current and alternative production routes in the context of decarbonization. Progress: 60% complete
	3 João Victor MENEZES CUNHA, Eric PIRARD, Thomas DRNEK; Refractories recycling: Fragmentation study. Progress: 0% complete
02	1 Sarah BADIOLI, Md JUBAYED, Marielle DARGAUD, Rinus SIEBRING, Angélique LÉONARD Carbon footprint vs Life Cycle Assessment: State of the art, challenges and future direction of environmental assessments of refractory materials Progress: 80% complete
	2 Sarah BADIOLI, Marielle DARGAUD, Thibault CHAMPION, Angélique LÉONARD Comparative Cradle-to-Gate Life Cycle Assessment of Refractory Bricks in Electric Arc Furnace Steelmaking Progress: 20% complete
	3 Sarah BADIOLI, Marielle DARGAUD, Thibault CHAMPION, Angélique LÉONARD Framework Proposal for Cradle-to-Grave Life Cycle Assessment of Refractory Products Progress: 10% complete
03	1 Sarah BADIOLI, Md JUBAYED, Marielle DARGAUD, Rinus SIEBRING, Angélique LÉONARD Carbon footprint vs Life Cycle Assessment: State of the art, challenges and future direction of environmental assessments of refractory materials

		Progress: 80% complete
	2	Md JUBAYED, Kinga KLIMA, Rinus SIEBRING, Angélique LÉONARD A Comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment Framework for Analysing the Environmental Impact of Refractories in the Steel Industry, with a Case Study on Magnesite-Carbon Bricks for Steel Ladle Lining Progress: 50% complete
	3	Md JUBAYED, Somansh CHORDIA, Kinga KLIMA, Rinus SIEBRING, Angélique LÉONARD A new methodological framework for decision support combining economic and environmental aspects of a product from consumer perspective Progress: 20% complete
04	1	Mathilda DERENSY, Thorsten TONNESEN, Jesus GONZALEZ-JULIAN New approach of recycling vanadium-bearing slags as a binder in high-alumina refractory castables application Accepted for publication - International Journal of Ceramic Engineering and Science, 2024
	2	Mathilda DERENSY, Thorsten TONNESEN, Application of vanadium-bearing slag in cement industry as an hydraulic cement, Progress: 40% complete
	3	Mathilda DERENSY, Thorsten TONNESEN Use of vanadium-bearing slags aggregates in refractory castables application, Progress: 15% complete
05	1	Andrea SALERNO, Kwasi Addo BOATENG, Mossaab MOUIYA, Paul LEPLAY, Amelie BIGEARD, Bart BOLLEN, Joerg SAUER, Marc HUGER Improving elastic moduli resonant frequency damping analysis measurements at high temperature via laser doppler vibrometer sensor Target Journal: Optics and Lasers in Engineering (Elsevier Ltd) Progress — 30% complete
	2	Andrea SALERNO, Martiniano PICICCO, Nicolas TESSIER-DOYEN, Lionel REBOUILLAT, Elsa THUNE, Severine ROMERO-BAIVIER, Salvatore GRECO, Marc HUGER Closing the Loop of Refractory Wastes In the Context of Steel Making and European Green Deal Target Journal: WIRES (Wiley) Progress - 60% complete
	3	Andrea SALERNO, Martiniano PICICCO, Elsa THUNE, Severine ROMERO-BAIVIER, Marc HUGER, Salvatore GRECO Multi Criteria Decision Method Applied to Tundish Working Lining Refractories to Evaluate Recycling Feasibility through the UTA Method Progress - 10% complete
06	1	Kwasi BOATENG, Jean-Michel AUVRAY, Christoph WÖHRMEYER, Elsa THUNE, Nicolas TESSIER-DOYEN, Marc HUGER Microcrack-induced thermomechanical behaviour of alumina refractory castables Progress - 20% complete
	2	Kwasi BOATENG, Jean-Michel AUVRAY, Christoph WÖHRMEYER, Nicolas TESSIER-DOYEN, Elsa THUNE, Marc HUGER Influence of aggregate type on calcium hexaluminate formation in alumina refractory castables. Progress - 20% complete
	3	Kwasi BOATENG, Jean-Michel AUVRAY, Christoph WÖHRMEYER, Nicolas TESSIER-DOYEN, Elsa THUNE, Marc HUGER Microstructural Insights using EBSD on alumina aggregates for refractory applications Progress - 10% complete
07	1	EWNETE Molla, CASTELNAU Olivier, PENG Hong, THUNE Elsa, GUINEBRETIERE Rene Alumina-magnesia reactive sintering kinetics and for innovative refractory ceramics at high temperatures Progress - 10% complete
	2	EWNETE Molla, CASTELNAU Olivier, PENG Hong, THUNE Elsa, GUINEBRETIERE Rene Developing cement-free alumina refractory castables using a novel microsilica binder Progress - 40% complete
	3	EWNETE Molla, CASTELNAU Olivier, PENG Hong, THUNE Elsa, GUINEBRETIERE Rene Investigation of high-temperature kinetics in alumina-magnesia reactive sintering using tomography imaging and synchrotron facilities Progress - 10% complete
08	1	Harikeshava RANGANATHAN, Damien ANDRE, Marc HUGER, Ratana SOTH, Christoph WÖHRMEYER Discrete element modeling deepens understanding of microcracking phenomena in refractory materials, American Ceramic Society Bulletin 2024, 103(2): 26–30. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10782900
	2	Harikeshava RANGANATHAN, Damien ANDRE, Marc HUGER, Ratana SOTH, Christoph WÖHRMEYER Anisotropic coefficient of thermal expansion mismatch-induced diffused damage in a polycrystalline microstructure design: Discrete element thermo-mechanical modelling Progress 20% complete
	3	Harikeshava RANGANATHAN, Damien ANDRE, Marc HUGER, Ratana SOTH, Christoph WÖHRMEYER A study to insight on the role of porosity on the sustainability of the refractory microstructure using Discrete Element Method

		Progress 0% complete
09	1	Michiel SMEDES, Wen ZHANG, Dietmar GRUBER, Aliz PINTO MORA On the use of temperature to destabilize deflocculated alumina in colloidal silica suspension in zero cement castables Effect of the matrix on mullite morphology in compare green, pre-fired and sintered samples Progress: 80% complete
	2	Michiel SMEDES, Wen ZHANG, Dietmar GRUBER, Aliz PINTO MORA Effect of silica fume in a zero-cement matrix on the mullite morphology in alumino-silicate castables Progress: 20% complete
	3	Michiel SMEDES, Wen ZHANG, Dietmar GRUBER, Aliz PINTO MORA Effect of mullite morphology in a zero-cement on thermomechanical properties in the manufacturing of turbine blades Progress: 40% complete
10	1	Paula CAMPOS DE OLIVEIRA, Wen ZHANG, Henning MARKÖTTER, Clément REMACHA, Giovanni BRUNO Advances in ceramic cores for aerospace applications: linking microstructure, processing, and properties Progress: 40% complete
	2	Paula CAMPOS DE OLIVEIRA, Wen ZHANG, Henning MARKÖTTER, Clément REMACHA, Giovanni BRUNO Microstructural characterisation of silica-based ceramic cores using synchrotron X-ray tomography Progress: 20% complete
	3	Paula CAMPOS DE OLIVEIRA, Henning MARKÖTTER, Wen ZHANG, Clément REMACHA, Giovanni BRUNO Synchrotron X-ray tomography for in-situ microstructural evolution of ceramic cores Progress: 0% complete
11	1	Cristian BOHORQUEZ, Dietmar GRUBER, Sido SINNEMA, Kinga KLIMA Hydrogen's Influence on microstructure and Young's Modulus evolution in a Phosphate Bonded Silica-containing high Alumina refractory Progress: 90% complete
	2	Cristian BOHORQUEZ, Dietmar GRUBER, Kinga KLIMA Study of the effect of hydrogen on fracture mechanics at room temperature in a phosphate-bonded refractory material Progress: 10% complete
	3	Cristian BOHORQUEZ, Dietmar GRUBER, Kinga KLIMA Study of the effect of hydrogen on creep and fracture mechanics at various temperatures Progress: 0% complete
12	1	Milena RIBEIRO GOMES, Tim LEBER, Tobias TILLMANN, Dorothea KENN, Daniela GAVAGNIN, Thorsten TONNESEN, Jesus GONZALEZ-JULIAN Towards H₂ implementation in the iron- and steelmaking industry: State of the art, requirements, and challenges for refractory materials Journal of the European Ceramic Society, 2024, 44 (3), 1307-1334 https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10103040
	2	Milena RIBEIRO GOMES, Thorsten TONNESEN, Daniela GAVAGNIN The catalytic effect of Fe impurities on the hydrogen corrosion of refractories Progress: 10% complete
	3	Milena RIBEIRO GOMES, Thorsten TONNESEN, Daniela GAVAGNIN Behaviour of different refractory binding systems under hydrogen atmospheres Progress: 0% complete
13	1	Amit Kumar GOPE, Alexandre BOULLE, Johan RICHAUD, Felix BIRKELBACH, Lionel REBOUILLAT, Severine ROMERO BAIVIER, Marc HUGER Process Parameter Prediction for Clogging in Steelmaking: A Data-Driven Approach Using Machine Learning Techniques Progress: 20% complete
	2	Amit Kumar GOPE, Alexandre BOULLE, Johan RICHAUD, Felix BIRKELBACH, Lionel REBOUILLAT, Severine ROMERO BAIVIER, Marc HUGER Predictive Modelling of Clogging in Continuous Casting: A Parameter-Based Machine Learning Framework Progress: 10% complete
	3	Amit Kumar GOPE, Alexandre BOULLE, Johan RICHAUD, Felix BIRKELBACH, Lionel REBOUILLAT, Severine ROMERO BAIVIER, Marc HUGER Current applications on deep learning techniques in Continuous casting system: A review Progress: 0% complete
14	1	Fatemeh AZIZI, Marvin GENNESSON, Damien WAGNER, Felix BIRKELBACH, René HOFMANN Enhancing Steel Ladle Thermal Management through Dimensionality Reduction: Advanced Techniques for Temperature Monitoring in Secondary Metallurgy Progress - 60% complete
	2	Fatemeh AZIZI, Marvin GENNESSON, Damien WAGNER, Felix BIRKELBACH, René HOFMANN Intelligent Reheating Optimization in Steelmaking: A Reinforcement Learning Approach to Minimize Heat Losses Progress - 15% complete
	3	Fatemeh AZIZI, Marvin GENNESSON, Damien WAGNER, Felix BIRKELBACH, René HOFMANN

		Hybrid Modeling for Steel Temperature Prediction: Integrating Machine Learning with Ladle Physical Models for Enhanced Thermal Management Progress - 0% complete
15	1	Victor RUELA, Paul van BEURDEN, Sido SINNEMA, Rene HOFMANN, Felix BIRKELBACH A global solution approach to the energy-efficient ladle dispatching problem with refractory temperature control IEEE Access, 2023, 11, 137718 https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3339392
	2	Victor RUELA, Paul van BEURDEN, Bruno LUCHINI, Rene HOFMANN, Felix BIRKELBACH Optimizing the steel ladle thermal management: towards a sustainable and cost-effective ladle fleet logistics Steel Research International, 2024, Accepted for publication
	3	Victor RUELA, Paul van BEURDEN, Rene HOFMANN, Felix BIRKELBACH Steel ladle fleet maintenance optimization Progress - 20% complete
Other	1	Michel RIGAUD, Jacques POIRIER, Marc HUGER, Thorsten TONNESEN, Victor PANDOLFELLI A refractory engineering program for the 21 st century Open Ceramics, 2023, 15, 100387 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceram.2023.100387
	2	Marc HUGER*, Glyn DERRICK, Mossaab MOUIYA, Andrea SALERNO, Kwasi Addo BOATENG, Harikeshava RANGANATHAN, Amit Kumar GOPE How Marie Skłodowska-Curie Doctoral Networks Can Support European Refractory Ecosystem in Context of The European Green Deal China's Refractories, 2024, 33 (2), 1-9 http://dx.doi.org/10.19691/j.cnki.1004-4493.2024.02.001

4 Conclusion

The cutting-edge research being carried out in the CESAREF project is currently being widely disseminated at conferences around the world. The DCs have presented their work at prestigious international conferences in Panama, Ireland, Germany, France, Croatia and Italy and will continue to do so in China and India before the end of 2024. The target of writing 3 full publications in Q1 ranked international journals will become the focus for the DCs as they approach the end of their 36-month research period. That being said, with already five articles published, two accepted for publication and one under review the CESAREF project is in a good position to achieve the target of 3 publications per DC. The dissemination will thus continue over the coming months and years, by attending further international conferences in 2025 and the completion of the planned publications already at different stages of the writing process.